

COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS OF METTL5 GENE VARIANTS
IMPLICATED IN INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY

Saima¹, Muhammad Haris Ali Khan², Rimsha Kanwal³, Shafaq Saqib⁴,
Syed Muhammad Waleed⁵, Humayoun Huma Maqbool^{*6}, Syeda Nida Fatima^{*7},
Mureed Hussain⁸

¹Department of Botany, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan

^{2,5}Institute of Botany, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

³Department of Zoology, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan

^{4, *6, *7}Institute of Zoology, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

⁸Department of Life Sciences, School of Science, University of Management and Technology, Lahore, Pakistan

^{*6}humayounmaqbool@gmail.com, ^{*7}fnida5853@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Humayoun Huma

Maqbool

Syeda Nida Fatima

Abstract

Its relationship to intellectual impairment (ID) in people is METTL5. Mutations in METTL5 have been linked to mild to severe forms of ID, which can manifest as deformities, seizures, microcephaly, short stature, and muscular hypotonia. The METTL5 gene is present on chromosome no 2. The METTL5 gene form a complex with TRMT112 and work normally. Due to knockdown of TRMT112 molecule the METTL5 gene expression is low in the body. In this study, bioinformatics approach has been used to predicted the coding and non-coding variants that effect the function, stability, splice site and non-coding region of METTL5 gene. A total of 66 missense variants in METTL5 gene were predicted to be pathogenic by CADD and meta-SNP. These mutations were analyzed by CUPSAT, Dynamut and Duet for their effect on stability and variations were predicted pathogenic overall. 60 of the 61 variations were predicted to be affecting the function of the gene by Mutpred. 5 variations D49Y, D103G, L76W, G130E and K194N were predicted by ScanProsite and NetSurf to affecting the PTM mechanism of the protein. These 61 missense variants were visualized by Chimera. CADD predicted 15 splice site variants out of which 10 were pathogenic and further analyzed for their effect by SPiCE v2.1, Splice AI and Mutation Taster. None of variations with uncertain significance found in splice site were predicted to affecting the splicing mechanism of the gene. The Regulome DB was used for the analysis of non-coding variants and predicted that less effect on the TF binding site of METTL5 gene. Data can be used for the early detection of mutations in METTL5 by cloning the mutation individually and determining their effect in vectors by mutagenesis. These findings contribute to our understanding of METTL5 gene representing complex disease features. This study demonstrated the importance of bioinformatics in determining highly pathogenic variants associated with the functional and structural relationship of METTL5.

Introduction

Intellectual functioning is the whole ability to understand and interact with reality. The

intelligence quotient (IQ) is a common metric for intellectual performance. The intelligence quotient (IQ) measures a person's overall

performance on standardized exams (IQ tests) designed to measure intellect. The standard deviation is 15 and the median score on the IQ test is 100. A score of 70 or below (two standard deviations below the median) denotes cognitive impairment. Deficits in intellectual function and adaptive behavior, which initially show up during embryonic development, are the hallmarks of intellectual disability (ID). These disabilities begin at birth, manifest before the age of 18, and have a variety of coexisting conditions, including meningitis, neurological disorders like infantile cerebral palsy, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, and autism spectrum disorders, as well as mental health conditions like depression and anxiety. (Naz and others, 2021)

These disabilities show up as a deficiency in social, cognitive, and practical skills. Social skills include things like interpersonal skills, social responsibility, self-esteem, gullibility, naivete, the capacity to address social problems, and the ability to abide by social standards and the law. Concepts include things like time, money, and language understanding. Practical skills include using tools, carrying out everyday duties, and engaging with people. All of these skills are acquired throughout the course of a person's life and are used to tackle simple or challenging tasks, regular problems, and social expectations. The age-related rise in these behavioral reactions. Several well-known methods are useful for figuring out the boundaries of adaptive behavior. (Lee *et al.* 2019)

In Western countries, 0.3-0.5% of the population has severe impairment (IQ 50), whereas 1.5-2% of the population has ID (IQ 70). Numerous studies have indicated that the prevalence of ID is thought to be much greater in developing countries.

2.5% of Pakistan's population possesses an ID, and of them, around 55% are from the Punjab province and 28.4% are from Sind, according to the National Census of Pakistan 1998. The incidence rate of ID might range from a mild case to a significant case (19.1/1000) (65/1000). (Naz *et al.*, 2021)

It's possible that some children with mild ID won't be discovered until they're 5 to 9 years old (16). The potential of an underlying brain

disability should be raised by physical abnormalities like macrocephaly or microcephaly, dysmorphic features, many congenital deformities, or feeding difficulties in a baby. While language, learning, academic challenges, and behavioral problems are typical pre-school and early-school manifestations of ID in children. Infancy-related ID frequently presents as gross motor delay. (Patel *et al.*, 2020)

People with profound intellectual disability commonly have congenital diseases. These people require constant supervision and help with self-care. They can't live a free life. There are usually physical limitations. They can communicate only in extremely limited ways. Persons with mild to moderate impairments are less likely to have concurrent medical problems than persons with severe or profound ID. (Boat *et al.* 2015)

The causes of ID are numerous. Among the genetic causes include genetic abnormalities like aneuploidies, copy number variations (CNVs), and tandem repeats in certain genes. DNA mutation is a mediator of genetic plasticity. The growth of tandem repeats can result in a number of ID-related disorders, including XLinked ID (XLID), various ataxias, motor neuron disease, and epilepsy. Tandem repeat polymorphisms (TRPs), which have recently come to light, may contribute to the missing heritability of polygenic illnesses. ID can also be caused by a variety of metabolic components, nucleotide repeat expansions, and changes in the mitochondrial DNA.

An error in cell division can result in an extra copy of chromosome 21 and cause a trisomy called Down's syndrome. It is the most often used type of ID. The clinical symptoms of Down's syndrome include dysmorphic traits, seizures, psychomotor slowness, and congenital deformity. It's probable that not everyone who is impacted has these ailments. Newborns with the chromosome 18 trisomy known as Edwards syndrome have brain damage that affects their psychomotor and cognitive development. Every 8,000 live births, one is affected by the Edwards syndrome. Only 510 percent of kids with this condition live through their first birthday. This demonstrates the high mortality rate it carries. (Hu *et al.*, 2019).

The term "CNV" refers to a small, variable segment of DNA. A copy from each parent's side and a copy from the maternal side are normally carried by each person. To alter the copy number, the small DNA segments can be copied and deleted. However, not all copy numbers, including deletions and duplications, are hazardous to people. DGV is the biggest CNV database. Online access is available.

CNVs that cause hereditary and de novo mutations have been linked to ID. In research on a sizable population, 118 uncommon de novo CNVs were discovered. The evaluation of these reported CNVs and putative genes led to the discovery of 10 genes with function loss associated with ID. CNVs cannot be spotted or found with a light microscope. Chromosome-level CNVs gain or loss can be discovered utilizing array C, which can swiftly and thoroughly analyses the whole genome. In recent years, array CGH analysis of unresolved ID cases has resulted in an up to 13% increase in the detection of pathogenic CNV. The characteristics associated with 13% of cases are congenital defects, major microcephaly, and low height (Hehir-Kwa et al., 2011).

This category of illnesses is genetically diverse. Both syndromic and non-syndromic forms of it are possible. Intellectual difficulties occur in conjunction with a variety of other phenotypic traits and are classified as the syndromic type of ID. Non-syndromic ID is the absence of accompanying pathology. Some genes and non-syndromic ID are related. In order to comprehend the typical diversity in IQ, these genes are being researched. They are connected to IQ (intelligence quotient). One way to examine the autosomal recessive etiology of ID in consanguineous families with afflicted siblings is using homozygosity mapping (Jamar et al., 2018)

The inheritance pattern known as autosomal dominant ID occurs when a person carries one copy of a mutant allele and one copy of a normal allele on a gene. Autosomal dominant ID is produced by heterozygous mutations in multiple known genes and CNVs. Tuberous sclerosis, neurofibromatosis, and myotonic dystrophy are autosomal dominant conditions connected to ID. A 200 kb deletion in exon 6

of a female patient revealed by SNP microarray analysis of the methyl binding domain gene on chromosome 2q23.1 was associated with autosomal dominant ID. It is difficult to determine the projected frequency of mutations in autosomal dominant ID genes.

When a person possesses one copy of a mutant allele and one copy of a normal allele on a gene, this inheritance pattern is known as autosomal dominant ID. Heterozygous mutations in numerous identified genes and CNVs generate autosomal dominant ID. Autosomal dominant diseases associated with ID include myotonic dystrophy, neurofibromatosis, and tuberous sclerosis. SNP microarray analysis of the methyl binding domain gene on chromosome 2q23.1 displayed that a 200 kb deletion in exon 6 of a female patient was linked with autosomal dominant ID. Finding the predicted frequency of mutations in autosomal dominant ID genes is challenging (Wieczorek et al., 2018).

The 5% of the human genome devoted to the X chromosome is associated with an expanding number of hereditary diseases. A 10-12% proportion of X chromosomal genes have been associated with ID. On chromosome Xq27.3, the FMR1 gene's 5' untranslated region (UTR) is the site where an increase in CGG trinucleotide repeats results in the X-linked recessive fragile X syndrome, which is clinically categorized as ID. The patients have phenotypic signs such dysmorphic facial features and jutting ears. A protein that helps maintain the integrity of RNA is encoded by FMR1. It is necessary for both neuronal plasticity and brain expansion.

Patients who have low synaptic connections as a result of GABA suppression or stimulation brought on by a deficit in FMRP protein have syndromic symptoms. The number of novel X-linked ID genes discovered in recent years has increased significantly as a result of the use of NGS. More than 140 X-linked genes are allegedly present. (Ilyas et al., 2020)

A lot of study has been done recently on chromosomal abnormalities, CNVs, autosomal dominant, and X-linked forms of ID (ARID), but less has been done on autosomal recessive types of ID. Significant attempts have recently been undertaken. Recent estimates indicate that AR is thought to be the root cause of 13-

24% of ID cases in Europe. In populations where consanguinity is prevalent, this is thought to be the most frequent cause of ID. (Mir *et al.*,2014)

The environment itself can contribute to ID. These include being exposed to hazardous substances, becoming sick when pregnant, and UV radiation. Inadequate nutrition, cultural deprivation, and childhood infections like measles and meningitis are some factors that might contribute to nervous system dysfunction. Origins of ID are still unknown in 50% of people. Genetic factors are the most frequent reasons.

METTL5

The methyltransferase known as Mettl5 has been shown to add m⁶ A to a particular location on the 18S rRNA nucleotide A-1832, also known as m⁶ A₁₈₃₂.

METTL5 has a single class I methyltransferase domain with the classic Rossmann fold, a seven-stranded β -sheet in the middle, and four and two alpha helices on either side, respectively. It has a catalytic site (N126-F129), an active site (V16-T31), and a substrate binding site (D185-D199). The classic NPPF motif is present in the METTL5 catalytic site, much like it is in another N6-adenosine methyltransferases. In order to catalyze the addition of the methyl group from SAM at the N6 position of

adenosine, METTL5 interacts with its substrate, S-adenosyl-L-methionine (SAM), in the C-terminal region of the METTL5 β -sheet. As a result, 18S's 3' minor end has a m⁶ A₁₈₃₂ alteration. The decoding center, where tRNA anticodons interact with mRNA codons during translation, is a few nucleotides distant from this.

The tRNA methyltransferase subunit 11-2 (TRMT112) is METTL5's coactivator. This complex, which is structurally conserved across TRMT112 and its other interacting partners contains a sizable hydrophobic core and a parallel zipper. The METTL5-TRMT112 complex crystallized, and it was discovered that they form a conserved binding region around SAM. TRMT112 is expected to increase METTL5's binding to SAM because it stabilizes the 3-4 loop with its partner (Fig. 1a) (Shenal *et al.*,2021)

In a similar manner, TRMT112 and METTL5 were discovered to interact (Liao *et al.*,2018). The metabolic stability and activity of METTL5 depend on TRMT112. When TRMT112 was knocked down, METTL5 protein levels were decreased, and the activity of the methyltransferase on 18S rRNA was markedly elevated. This result shows that TRMT112 greatly enhances and stabilizes METTL5 catalytic activity, rather than being necessary for it (Van *et al.*,2019).

Figure 1: (PDB code 6H2U) shows the crystal structure of the human METTL5-TRMT112 complex.

Here, the proteins METTL5 and TRMT112 are shown in turquoise and purple, respectively. The METTL5 active site is depicted in orange, the substrate binding site is depicted in yellow, and the catalytic site is depicted in red. The color hot pink denotes S-

adenosylmethionine (SAM). The dark blue numbers METTL5 3 and TRMT112 4 are shown. b a zoomed-in picture of the interaction between SAM and the METTL5 catalytic site. No 18 S rRNA is shown. Except for the methyl group being shown in grey, the color scheme is

the same as in Example A. SAM, the catalytic site, and its methyl group are shown using a ball and stick diagram. Hydrogen is shown by the dotted lines (Turkalj *et al.*, 2022).

Tissue and Cellular Location of METTL5

METTL5 is found to have low but ubiquitous expression across all tissues throughout the adult human body, with the highest expression in the digestive tract, according to the Human

Protein Atlas project. examined METTL5 expression in tissues from 20- to 70-year-old patients, including brain, muscle, blood, heart, colon, and lung tissues¹⁸. They identified a significant reduction in the protein expression of METTL5 with age, which suggests that METTL5 may have higher expression in younger tissues and potentially even higher levels in early development.

Figure 1.2: Expression profile of METTL5 according to the Human Protein Atlas.

An Expression of METTL5 across tissues (image from the Human Protein Atlas: <https://www.proteinatlas.org/ENSG00000138382-METTL5/tissue>). b, c the subcellular expression profile of METTL5 shows its localization to nucleoli and cytoplasm (images from the Human Protein Atlas: <https://www.proteinatlas.org/ENSG00000138382-METTL5/subcellular>) (Turkalj *et al.*, 2022).

In humans, variants in METTL proteins have been associated with various disorders, such as sclerosis (METTL1[MIM: 404466] Alicna *et al.*,2013), liver cancer (METTL3[MIM: 612472]Chen *et al.*,2018), breast cancer (METTL3,Cai *et al.*,2018 METTL6 Gatza *et al.*,2014), colon cancer (METTL8 [MIM: 609525] and METTL16 Yeon *et al.*,2018), pancreatic cancer (METTL1331 [MIM: 617987] Liu *et al.*, 2019),

autoprojection/hearing loss (MIM: 605429,METTL13 Yousaf *et al.*,2018), and osteoporosis (METTL21C [MIM: 615259] Huang *et al.*,201). For instance, truncating alleles of METTL23 (MIM: 615262) have been identified in families with mild non-syndromic ARID or cognitive dysfunction with mild dysmorphic features (MIM: 615942). Similarly, micro-duplications (351 kb and 432 kb genomic region), both containing METTL4 among other genes, were associated with ID and mild dysmorphic features (Kashevarova *et al.*,2018). A recent study, using Mettl14 transgenic mice, showed that Mettl14 regulates the size of the brain and more particularly the size of the cerebral cortex, via altered histone modifications. Knocking out Mettl14 specifically in the neural stem cells leads to microcephaly (Wang *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, the ablation of Mettl3 in mice lead to

developmental defects associated with depletion of m⁶A and dramatic change in the expression of apoptosis and cerebellum development-related genes (Chen Xi Wang 2018). In addition to their roles in the regulation of brain development, both Mettl3 and Mettl14 are key molecules that can alter learning abilities (Koranda *et al.*, 2018). METTL3-METTL14 complex is one of the main components, but it does not account for all the N⁶-methyl adenosine (m⁶A) modifications. The identification of

METTL16, another methyltransferase-like protein, as a new m⁶A methyltransferase suggests that other methyltransferase-like family members like METTL5 may also carry m⁶A methyltransferase activity (Warda *et al.*, 2017).

Its relationship to intellectual impairment (ID) in people is METTL5. Mutations in METTL5 have been linked to mild to severe forms of ID, which can manifest as deformities, seizures, microcephaly, short stature, and muscular hypotonia.

Figure 1.3: Protein truncation brought on by METTL5 mutations results in a phenotype marked by intellectual impairment (ID) and microcephaly. The gene is shown with alternatively spliced sections in green, non-transcribed exon regions in pink, and protein-coding exons in purple. The SAM methyltransferase domain of the protein is shown in red, while the remaining portions of the protein are shown in blue. The early protein truncations brought on by the 2-bp deletions seen in humans result in the phenotype shown in the METTL5 mutant (Turkalj *et al.*, 2022).

Tools to Predict the Variations in METTL5

The variants in METTL5 are analyzed using a variety of techniques. Enormous databases are accessible to fulfill the need for mutation found in the human population. Databases are connected to other services and are available via the Internet. Data could be retrieved from Linvar, dBS, and nomad v2.1.1 at the first stage. The missense and splice site versions are downloaded separately. To find variations that have a high likelihood of being harmful, an allele frequency filter with a cutoff of 0.001 is used.

Combined Annotation Dependent Depletion (CADD) is widely used in scoring the human genome variants as pathogenic. At the genomic level, this technique is utilized to forecast damaging mutations as well as their addition and deletion of nucleotides. It incorporates several annotations into a single metric. It operates according to the principles of genetic

architecture, conservation, size, and variation effect (Entsch *et al.*, 2019). It generates a score for pathogenicity. Higher scores are more likely to have negative effects. CADD looked at the mutation in the reference assembly and produced two major scores. One is the C score (Raw) and the main Pared based C-Score (Scaled). A highly pathogenic variation is one with a Pared score above 20. (Entsch, Schaech, Shandra & Kircher *et al.*, 2021)

Missense analysis is done by using different computational tools to analyze the effect of mutation on protein functionality.

Meta-SNP is an in-silico tool. It is widely used for the detection of diseased SNPs which are non-synonymous. It has been used to determine whether a mutation is disease-related or a polymorphism. The output determines if the variation is related to a disease, then it is pathogenic and the

polymorphic is shown as neutral. Its output is based on four tools including SNAP, Panther, SIFT, and PhD-SNP. It is anticipated to be sick if its score is higher than 0.5 (Capriati *et al.*, 2013).

It is abbreviated as a computational method for consequence agonistic pathogenicity interpretation of clinical exome variation. It is a modern machine learning-based approach for identifying and prioritizing pathogenic variants. It forecasts the pathogenic variants on the basis of score. The score range is between 0 to 1, with 0 representing less pathogenic, 0.9 or 1 representing severely pathogenic, and 0.5 representing the threshold.

Posttranslational modifications (PTMs) are covalent processing processes that alter the characteristics of proteins by adding proteolytic cleavage. It is also done by adding a modifying group to one or more amino acids, such as acetyl, phosphoryl, glycosyl, and methyl. There are different types of PTM. Some main PTM types include phosphorylation, Methylation, N-acetylation, glycosylation, and ubiquitination. Several tools have been created to analyze the PTM sites in a protein structure. (Ramzi *et al.*, 2021)

The most common type of PTM is phosphorylation in which the phosphate group is covalently attached with a protein molecule. This type of PTM is mostly repeated in the life cycle of protein. It is a reversible PTM type that plays an important role in the activation or inactivation of enzymes and in the signaling of cells.

Another type of PTM is methylation. The Methyl group is covalently attached to the protein to perform its function. It plays a critical role in gene expression. It is reversible PTM. It often happens in cell nuclei and on the histone's proteins. Glycosylation is a reversible enzyme-directed reaction. In this modification, oligosaccharide chains are covalently joined to certain residues. It takes place in numerous subcellular sites including the endoplasmic reticulum, the Golgi apparatus, the cytoplasm, and the sarcolemma membrane. It plays a critical role in cell recognition. It also involves various regulatory functions. Acetylation has a vital role in biological processes such as nuclear transport, protein-protein interaction, and

chromatin stability. It is also important for cell development. (Ramzi *et al.*, 2021)

These post-translational modifications increase the functional diversity of the proteome. These changes are necessary for proteins to function properly or to be recognized by other enzymes. The structure and functionality of proteins are significantly impacted by these processes. PTM disruption can result in the malfunctioning of crucial biological processes and, as a result, in a number of diseases. The diseases can include cancer, mental retardation, Parkinson's disease, and neurological disorders. High-throughput experimental techniques for the discovery of PTMs are very labor-intensive. Therefore, it is essential to use effective tools and computational techniques to predict PTMs.

Different servers are used to predict modifications sites

1. Scan Posited
2. Uniport
3. UCSF Chimera
4. NetSurfP-2.0

Scan Posited is an online interface to identify protein matches against signatures from the Posited database. NetSurfP-2.0 tool predicts solvent availability, loops or helix, and secondary structures which are accessible in a protein structure (De Castroist *et al.*, 2006). is an effective tool for predicting the functional characteristics of proteins in the absence of related protein experimental structures (Siegrist *et al.*, 2012).

UCSF Chimera is extensively used for protein structure visualization. It is an open-accessible tool available for academic students and researchers. It shows other features including Multi Align View for Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA), View Dock involved in the visualization of ligand interaction with protein structure, and volume viewer that is used for analyzing volumetric data. (Pettersen *et al.*, 2004) Dynamite is an effective tool for the prediction of protein stability. It provides information about flexibility analysis and protein motion. It can also provide information about destabilizing variants. Its output also contains the score of three tools including MCSM, SDM, and duet. If the score

is greater than 0, then it is predicted as destabilizing (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2018).

Mutpred2 is an online tool. It is established to categorize an amino acid substitution as disease-associated or neutral in humans. It provides outcomes in the form of a score. If the score is greater than 0.50, then it would be suggested as pathogenic (Palaver *et al.*, 2020).

Splice Site Analysis tools are used to predict the mutation in splice region. During transcription, pre-mRNA is spliced by the spliceosome and matured by the splicing of introns. The remaining exons are pasted together by spliceosome to make the final mature mRNA (Reed *et al.*, 1996). Introns contain a splice Donor site and a splice acceptor site. The 5' end of the intron is the splice donor site and the 3' end is the splice acceptor site (Wichita *et al.*, 2019). Splicing proteins identify particular regions. If a mutation happens at this stage, it either causes intron retention or exon skipping. Intron retention takes place when a mutation is located a in small intron such that combination of the intron and the flanking upstream and downstream exon is considered as an exon. This can happen due to limiting spliceosome, weak splice sites, and short intron length. Exon skipping happens when acceptor site mutated near one end of exon so, it no longer remains as the acceptor site, and the donor site near the same exon mutated, so it is no longer a donor site. When splicing occurs, the entire section spliced out including the exon as well (Wong *et al.*, 2016). The analysis of the splice site is done by using the following computational tools.

SPICE is used to provide us with information about the pathogenic variants. It can predict the spliceogenicity of variations situated at the 5' and 3' splice sites. Its results are presented as a graph that demonstrates whether the variations fall within the pathogenic or tolerated part. It also provides the score of each variant with its precise threshold value. The threshold is set on the graph. The variants below the threshold are considered neutral while variants over the threshold are designated as pathogenic (Leman *et al.*, 2018). Splice is a deep neural network. It can accurately predict splice junctions from an

arbitrary pre-mRNA transcript sequence. It aids in the accurate prediction of noncoding genetic variants that can cause cryptic splicing. The results for each variant appear as Acceptor Loss, donor loss, acceptor gain, and donor gain. Acceptor loss and Donor loss mean that intron retention occurs during the splicing of mRNA. Donor gain happened due to an inappropriate 5' splice site and it results in exon skipping. Acceptor gain happened due to an inappropriate 3' splice site and it results in exon skipping. Each type has assigned a specific delta score. Delta scores range from 0 to 1. It can be interpreted as the probability that the variant will have an impact on splicing at any point in a window surrounding it. If the delta score is greater than 0.2, then variants predict to affect splicing. (Jagannathan *et al.*, 2019)

Mutation Taster is a web tool used to predict the pathogenic variants in the splice region. It can predict the change in pathogenic regions and provide the probability of disease occurrence as well (Steinhaus *et al.*, 2021).

Regulome DB 2.0 is a web tool used to predict the SNPs variants in the non-coding region (Boyle *et al.*, 2012)

The protein function affects by mutation in the coding SNPs, we analyzed the coding and non-coding SNPs. The process of translation and transcription could be affected by mutation in non-coding region. Due to mutation, the alteration occurs in regulatory regions, 5 prime UTRs or 3prime UTRs. The phenotypic feature can be altered.

In silico analysis of this gene has been done to predict the coding and non-coding variants which are involved in ID.

Methodology

To study the variants in METTL5, a variety of bioinformatic tools have been utilized. For variants analysis, we need to retrieve the variants. Variants can be retrieved from databases such as GnomAD, Variation Viewer, Clinvar, and dbSNP. In our study, we used the gnomAD, and dbSNP. database for retrieval or variants. The missense and splice site variants were retrieved and downloaded separately in CSV formats. The variants from GnomAD were filtered, and only those variants were retained whose allele frequency was 0.001

because the allele frequency of METTL5 in the human population is less than 1%. The links for these databases are:

Variation Selection

The variants from all these databases have been combined into the same file. Only the RSID and position of these variants were copied from the Variation viewer and pasted into the GnomAD file. The positions of all combined variations are categorized from largest to smallest according to their chromosomal location. The duplicated variants are also deleted from the combined file.

Combined Annotation Dependent Depletion (CADD)

CADD is a variant annotation tool. It assigns a score based on how harmful single nucleotide variations (SNV). CADD incorporates a variety of annotations, and grading is based on a variety of factors, including conservation and missense alterations, among others. By giving each variant a C-score, CADD annotation produces a result that predicts the variant’s true pathogenicity. Intron and exon pathogenicity of the gene, as well as allelic diversity, are correlated with the C-score.

Variants having a CADD score greater than or equal to 20 are thought to be pathogenic (Kircher *et al.*, 2014)

In this study, the variants from the combined file were submitted on CADD for annotation.

The scoring did in VCF format. The results were downloaded in CSV format. In the output file, I applied some filters to remove unnecessary variants. A filter on the gene column was applied and only those variants that have METTL5 kept. Another filter applied on Cons Details and only missense and splice missense remained checked. Another filter on PHRED score of greater than or equal to 20 was also applied to filter out only highly pathogenic variants. These variants incorporated in the finalized file that contain missense variants.

For the analysis of pathogenic variants, there are many online tools that operate on various algorithms. In this study, two highly accurate tools used for missense analysis. CADD output used as an input.

Meta-SNP

Meta-SNP is an online tool that can help to discriminate between polymorphic nonsynonymous SNVs and SNVs that are linked to disease. Meta-SNP was created as a meta-predictor that improved the detection of harmful mutations by combining the results of the PANTHER, PhD-SNP, SIFT, and SNAP. In this study, the input provided on the online Meta-SNP server. The output downloaded in the form of a text file. For the exposure of most deleterious variants, a threshold of 0.5 applied. Variants that have probability greater than 50 % kept.

Table: Pathogenicity score of CADD and MetaSNP

Sr. No	Missense Tools	Pathogenicity Score
1	CADD	>20
2	Meta-SNP	>0.5
3	Panther	>0.5
4	PHD-SNP	>0.5
5	SIFT	>0.5
6	SNP	>0.5

Stability Analysis

The missense variations can affect the protein stability as a result affecting the function of protein. Multiple computational tools are available for predicting the effect of mutations on protein stability. The tools used for stability

prediction in this research are Dynamut, Cupsat, hope and Duet. These tools predict the stability of protein based on Gibb’s free energy.

DynaMut

DynaMut is an online tool. It gives information about the impact of mutation on protein stability. The finalized missense variants used as an input for stability analysis. The output of DynaMut provides the vibrational entropy of the modify residues in Gibbs free energy. All variants with energy less than 0 are considered as destabilizing. If score comes in negative value, then missense variation affects the stability of protein. (Weffenstette *et al.*, 2018).

CUPSAT

Cupsat is another stability tool. For the input PDB ID 6H2U and thermal method was used

to predict stability of METTL5 mutations. Mutations with negative Gibb’s energy were predicted to be destabilizing the protein. Cupsat also provides information on the effect of mutation on torsion of protein either it is favourable or unfavourable.

DUET

Duet is also a stability predicting tool. For the stability production same PDB ID 6H2U was selected and mutations from chain A were run individually. The mutations with negative Gibb’s free energy were predicted destabilizing. After running all the tools, the scores for each mutation from all the tools were compiled into an excel file.

Table 3.2: Cut-of values of stability tools used to predict the destabilizing variant.

	Stability Predicting Tools	Destabilizing Score
1	Dynamut	>0
2	Cupsat	>0
3	Duet	>0

Functional Analysis

The functionality of protein can be affected by the missense variations. These mutations can affect the region of proteins which has important contribution toward the function of the protein. In this study, Mutpred2 is used to predict the change in functionality of protein.

Mutpred2

Mutpred2 is machine-based learning. It is used to predict pathogenicity of amino acid substitutions and their impact on molecular mechanisms. The effects of each variant on more than 50 different protein properties can be predicted by Mutpred2. In the Mupred, the score greater than 0.5 have probability of more than 50% to be pathogenic. In this study, missense variants used as an input to ran on Mutpred2 for functional analysis (Mort *et al.*, 2014).

Post Translational Modification Analysis

Mutations in the motif of proteins can interrupt with post-translational modification of the protein and also affect functioning of protein. In this study, I use three different types for PTM analysis of METTL5 protein.

For PTM analysis, the FASTA sequence of METTL5 protein retrieved from Uniprot. This FASTA sequence used as an input for ScanProsite. Another tool Netsurf 2.0 used to check if the amino acids present in the PTM site motif are exposed or buried. In the end, we confirm which missense variants lie in the PTM site motif given by ScanProsite and later check these variants buried or exposed through NetSurf 2.0. If motif of PTM site is disturbed due to missense variation then we will visualize these mutations using UCSF Chimera.

Mutagenesis Analysis of METTL5 Gene by Using UCSF Chimera

UCSF chimera is a program for interactive visualization. In this study, UCSF chimera is used to find out the effect of mutation in protein structure. It is done by comparing the mutated and wild type residue. If a missense mutation occurs in the protein, it may create pseudo bonds or clashes with adjacent residues. I analyzed all the missense variants on UCSF chimera to check either producing clashes with other residues or not. Firstly, I used Rotamer command in UCSF chimera to mutate wild type residue. After that, possible

clashes produced by mutated residue with neighboring zones analyzed by using “Find Clashes/Contacts” command. I minimize the structure up to 100 minimization steps and 10 conjugate gradient steps if a mutated residue exhibits clashes to determine the proper molecular arrangement in space.

Splice Site Analysis

Coding and non-coding regions, sometimes referred to as exome and introns, are present in the genomes of higher eukaryotes and mammals. After transcription, pre mRNA contains intron and exons. An enzyme spliceosome at specific reorganization site in mRNA removes introns from mRNA and joins the exons together. The 5' donor site (GU) and 3' acceptor site (AG) are these recognition sites. Mutations in these splice sites influence mRNA splicing and may lead to proteins with changed functions (Diederichs *et al.*, 2016). In this study, I use in-silico tools to analyze the pathogenic splice site variants in the METTL5 gene and their effect on the splicing of mRNA.

Retrieving Splice Site Variants

For splice site analysis, I retrieved variants data from gnomAD and the result is downloaded in CSV file. In gnomAD file, I applied filters on genome column and only checked pass. Another filter applied on “VEP annotation” and I only checked splice site variants. After applying these filters, I had only splice region variants. These variants used as input for CADD for score annotation. The output of CADD opened in excel sheet to apply some filters to keep only highly pathogenic variants. The first filter applied on “ConsDetail” and only splice/intron remains checked. Another filter applied on “Gene Name” column and only name of the gene remained checked. Last

filter applied on PHRED score of greater than >10 and the remaining pathogenic splice site variants noted down. Further, analysis of splice site mutations done by using these variants from CADD. In this study, I used SPiCEv2.1, SpliceAI and Mutation Taster to check what possible effect these splice site variants can cause in splicing of METTL5 gene.

SPiCEv2.1

SPiCEv2.1 is used to predict the effect of mutation on splicing. First, SPiCEv2.1 downloaded from an offline tool. After the installation, I run it as an administrator. After that, I had chosen assembly 37 and provided the input by using CADD file. The output was provided in the form of graph threshold value of pathogenicity fixed in it. Variants that lie above the threshold line have high probability to affect the splicing while those that are below the threshold line are considered as neutral.

SpliceAI

SpliceAI is an online tool to analyze splicing. The input provided by using the highly deleterious variants obtained from CADD. Each variant submitted separately. The results for each variant appear as Acceptor Loss, donor loss, acceptor gain, and donor gain. Each type has assigned a specific delta score. If the delta score is greater than 0.2, then variants predict to affect splicing (Jaganathan *et al.*, 2019).

Mutation Taster

It is an online tool to evaluate the disease-causing potential of sequence alterations. The input provided as a chromosome no, position, ref and alt in combined form. The results were appeared in form of type of mutation and probability score.

Figure: Flowchart of splice site variants analysis

Regulome DB 2.0

It is online tool to evaluate the SNPs that present in the 3 prime UTRs and 5 prime UTRs. The input provides a RS ID no. The result appeared in a table form in which every RSID no given a ranking (1a to 6). As the ranks increase, the affect of SNPs on TF binding lessens. The rank 2a, 2b, 3a, 4 and 5 are

support by TF binding + matched TF motif + matched DNase Footprint + DNase peak, TF binding + any motif + DNase Footprint + DNase peak, TF binding + any motif + DNase peak, TF binding + DNase peak, and TF binding or DNase peak data respectively by Regulome server.

Table: Computational tool and their chrome address use in this research

GnomAD	https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/
dbSNP	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/?cmd=search
Meta-SNP	Meta-SNP - Meta-predictor of disease causing variants (biofold.org)
DynaMut	https://biosig.lab.uq.edu.au/dynamut/
DUET	http://structure.bioc.cam.ac.uk/duet
Mutepred	http://mutpred.mutdb.org/index.html#qform
Uniprot	https://www.uniprot.org/
Scan Prosite	https://prosite.expasy.org/scanprosite/
NetSurf 2.0	: https://services.healthtech.dtu.dk/services/NetSurfP-2.0/
UCSF Chimera	https://www.cgl.ucsf.edu/chimera/
SPiCEv2.1	https://sourceforge.net/projects/spicev2-1/
SpliceAI	https://spliceailookup.broadinstitute.org/
Regulome DB 2.0	http://www.regulomedb.org/

RESULTS

Missense Variants Analysis

Variants present in human genome can be retrieved by using multiple online databases. In this study, gnomAD and dpsnp to retrieve variants. From gnomAD, total 139 variants were retrieved and then filter applied on "Exome" column and checked only pass. Another filter of 0.001 on allele frequency was applied and only 139 variants remained. I used dpsnp and 228 variants were retrived. All these

variants were added in the gnomAD file and duplicates were removed. Total number of 296 variants remained in the combined file. These 296 variants used as an input for CADD score annotation. The output of CADD provided 844 variants. Filters were applied on this file, one was on the "Gene Name" column, here name of the gene checked while another filter applied on "CONS Detail" column here splice, missense / missense variants remained checked. Total number of 195 variants

remained after applying these filters. These variants were analysed on the missense analysis tools that includes MetaSNP. The results obtained from these tools combined along with CADD and the various filters applied on the output score of the variants from these tools. A filter of greater than or equal to 20 applied on the PHRED score of CADD, greater than 0.5 on the score of MetaSNP.

After applying filters, CADD showed 195 out of 884 variants, metaSNP showed 66 out of 194 diseased variants. The combined result of all these filters represents only 66 variants out of 194 . These 66 variants are used for the further analysis of stability and functionality.

Table: Missense Analysis of highly pathogenic variants using in-silico tools including CADD, MetaSNP, PANTHER, PHD-SNP, SIFT and SNAP.

p.Mutation	CADD	Meta-SNP Score	PANTHER	PHD-SNP	SIFT	SNAP
p.Arg206Trp	29.8 Disease	0.744 Disease	0.797 Disease	0.541 Disease	0 Disease	0.76 Disease
p.Val202Gly	32 Disease	0.756 Disease	0.648 Disease	0.718 Disease	0 Disease	0.785 Disease
p.His193Tyr	32 Disease	0.819 Disease	0.571 Disease	0.835 Disease	0 Disease	0.825 Disease
p.His164Pro	28.5 Disease	0.776 Disease	0.603 Disease	0.583 Disease	0.02 Disease	0.775 Disease
p.Leu156Ser	28.5 Disease	0.738 Disease	0.724 Disease	0.702 Disease	0 Disease	0.725 Disease
p.Ser155Cys	28.5 Disease	0.703 Disease	0.746 Disease	0.54 Disease	0 Disease	0.715 Disease
p.Ser155Tyr	29.6 Disease	0.778 Disease	0.782 Disease	0.704 Disease	0 Disease	0.745 Disease
p.Tyr154Ser	28.5 Disease	0.767 Disease	0.665 Disease	0.789 Disease	0.03 Disease	0.775 Disease
p.Gly130Glu	30 Disease	0.759 Disease	0.736 Disease	0.781 Disease	0 Disease	0.855 Disease
p.Pro127Arg	28.6 Disease	0.793 Disease	0.778 Disease	0.718 Disease	0 Disease	0.855 Disease
p.Asp121Gly	32 Disease	0.765 Disease	0.502 Disease	0.695 Disease	0.01 Disease	0.79 Disease
p.Asp108Val	32 Disease	0.753 Disease	0.572 Disease	0.815 Disease	0.03 Disease	0.73 Disease
p.Val105Gly	27.3	0.746	0.691	0.593	0.02	0.7

	Disease	Disease	Disease	Disease	Disease	Disease
p.Asn93His	27.3 Disease	0.75 Disease	0.775 Disease	0.666 Disease	0.02 Disease	0.745 Disease
p.Asp85His	29.8 Disease	0.551 Disease	0.615 Disease	0.518 Disease	0.04 Disease	0.505 Disease
p.Asp83Gly	31 Disease	0.755 Disease	0.638 Disease	0.924 Disease	0 Disease	0.67 Disease
p.Phe80Ser	30 Disease	0.554 Disease	0.459 Disease	0.541 Disease	0.09 Disease	0.52 Disease
p.Gly79Val	32 Disease	0.696 Disease	0.805 Disease	0.705 Disease	0.01 Disease	0.65 Disease
p.Gly68Arg	29.5 Disease	0.697 Disease	0.582 Disease	0.781 Disease	0.01 Disease	0.65 Disease
p.Leu65Arg	27.9 Disease	0.802 Disease	0.789 Disease	0.859 Disease	0 Disease	0.77 Disease
p.Leu65Pro	27.9 Disease	0.856 Disease	0.845 Disease	0.865 Disease	0 Disease	0.775 Disease
p.Gly63Glu	26.8 Disease	0.877 Disease	0.768 Disease	0.916 Disease	0 Disease	0.89 Disease
p.Gly61Asp	26.6 Disease	0.874 Disease	0.769 Disease	0.952 Disease	0 Disease	0.885 Disease
p.Gly59Ala	26.1 Disease	0.798 Disease	0.619 Disease	0.854 Disease	0.02 Disease	0.755 Disease
p.Gly59Glu	26.9 Disease	0.903 Disease	0.768 Disease	0.933 Disease	0 Disease	0.825 Disease
p.Gly59Arg	27.9 Disease	0.87 Disease	0.824 Disease	0.912 Disease	0 Disease	0.85 Disease
p.Asp57Val	26.9 Disease	0.856 Disease	0.8 Disease	0.926 Disease	0 Disease	0.785 Disease
p.Asp57Try	29 Disease	0.922 Disease	0.859 Disease	0.934 Disease	0 Disease	0.815 Disease
p.Asp49Tyr	29.7 Disease	0.822 Disease	0.79 Disease	0.912 Disease	0 Disease	0.755 Disease

p.Leu40Pro	27.7 Disease	0.788 Disease	0.679 Disease	0.855 Disease	0 Disease	0.735 Disease
p.Ala37Thr	37 Disease	0.51 Disease	0.27 Disease	0.726 Disease	0.13 Disease	0.225 Disease
p.Gln28His	25.3 Disease	0.749 Disease	0.744 Disease	0.623 Disease	0 Disease	0.8 Disease
p.Gln28Arg	31 Disease	0.703 Disease	0.518 Disease	0.644 Disease	0.02 Disease	0.7 Disease
p.Leu26Pro	32 Disease	0.731 Disease	0.845 Disease	0.805 Disease	0.02 Disease	0.605 Disease
p.Lys23Gln	29.9 Disease	0.538 Disease	0.547 Disease	0.484 Disease	0.04 Disease	0.51 Disease
p.Pro22Arg	31 Disease	0.744 Disease	0.807 Disease	0.656 Disease	0.02 Disease	0.755 Disease

CADD score>20, Meta-SNP , PANTHER, PHD-SNP, SNAP score>0.5 and SIFT score ≥ 0 are pathogenic and disease causing variants.

Figure: Pathogenicity Analysis results of CADD and Meta-SNP for missense variants.

Stability Analysis

Stability analysis on the final pathogenic missense variants was performed to check whether these missense mutations can create disturbance in the structure of protein. Various

web tools are available to check the destabilization of missense variants in the protein structure. Variants are considered destabilizing if they indicate a negative value. In this study, Cupsat, DynaMut, and DUET are

used. These tools provide output in the form of free energy.

Cupsat tool predicted that 17 were stabilizing, 1 was no change and 43 were destabilizing.

DynaMut tool predicted that 28 were destabilizing and 33 were stabilizing. Duet analysis predicted that 55 were destabilizing and 6 were stabilizing.

Table: Stability Analysis of highly stabilizing and destabilizing variants of *METTL5* using in-silico tools including Cupsat, DUET, and DynaMut.

Mutated Amino acid	Cupsat score Overall Stability	Duet score Overall Stability	Dynamut Score Overall Stability
p.Val202Gly	-5.85 Destabilizing	-3.427 Destabilizing	-2.792 Destabilizing
p.Arg183Gly	-2.74 Destabilizing	-0.327 Destabilizing	-0.285 Destabilizing
p.Leu156Ser	-5.06 Destabilizing	-4.1 Destabilizing	-3.686 Destabilizing
p.Met139Lys	-3.23 Destabilizing	-1.591 Destabilizing	-0.918 Destabilizing
p.Asp121Asn	-2.02 Destabilizing	-0.367 Destabilizing	-0.176 Destabilizing
p.Asp103Gly	-4.34 Destabilizing	-0.693 Destabilizing	-0.306 Destabilizing
p.Asn93His	-2.27 Destabilizing	-1.492 Destabilizing	-0.185 Destabilizing
p.Phe80Ser	-8.84 Destabilizing	-3.533 Destabilizing	-3.477 Destabilizing
p.Cys77Tyr	-1.56 Destabilizing	-1.102 Destabilizing	-0.454 Destabilizing
p.Gly68Arg	-1.94 Destabilizing	-1.245 Destabilizing	-0.586 Destabilizing
p.Ile67Ser	-4.63 Destabilizing	-3.672 Destabilizing	-3.409 Destabilizing
p.Leu65Pro	-10.39 Destabilizing	-2.273 Destabilizing	-1.124 Destabilizing
p.Gly63Glu	-3.52 Destabilizing	-2.037 Destabilizing	-0.91 Destabilizing
p.Gly61Asp	-3.16 Destabilizing	-2.378 Destabilizing	-0.324 Destabilizing
p.Tyr41Cys	0.91 Destabilizing	-1.392 Destabilizing	-1.196 Destabilizing
p.Leu40Pro	-4.47 Destabilizing	-2.04 Destabilizing	-1.66 Destabilizing
p.Cys38Gly	-1.17 Destabilizing	-2.393 Destabilizing	-1.737 Destabilizing
p.Ala37Thr	-3.68 Destabilizing	-2.148 Destabilizing	-0.526 Destabilizing
p.Arg32Trp	-0.01 Destabilizing	-0.275 Destabilizing	-0.375 Destabilizing
p.Glu27Gln	-0.47 Destabilizing	-0.801 Destabilizing	-0.651 Destabilizing

p.Lys23Gln	-0.05 Destabilizing	-0.35 Destabilizing	-0.153 Destabilizing
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Destabilizing variants score > 0 (the structure of protein affect)

Figure: Result of each missense tool showing the pathogenic missense variants of METTL5

- Destabilizing Variants (Due to missense mutation, these variants disturbed the stability of protein)
- Stabilizing Variants (These variants not disturbed the stability of protein after missense mutation)

Functional Analysis

Mutpred2 is used to check the disturbance in the function of the protein. The pathogenicity prediction range is greater than 0.50. The output provided in the form of a score and

prediction about the specific functional changes by missense variants is also given. In this study, variants retrieved from missense analysis analyzed on Mutpred2. The output was received in excel file. Mutpred2 predicted that 61 variants were pathogenic while 1 was non-pathogenic.

Most of the functional disturbance in pathogenic variants were Altered Metal binding, Altered Transmembrane protein and Altered Ordered interface. These changes affect the molecular mechanism of METTL5.

Figure: Graphical representation of pathogenic and non-pathogenic missense variants

- Total Variants (Pathogenic and non-pathogenic)
- Pathogenic Variants (These variants predicted score are more than 0.50)
- Non-Pathogenic Variants (This variant predicted score lower than 0.50)

PTM Site Analysis

The proper function of proteins is check by using post translation modification and the function of proteins may affect by mutations in

the PTM site. For PTM analysis Netsurf 2.0, ScanProsite and Uniprot are used. FASTA format of gene is use as input for Netsurf 2.0 and ScanProsite. It was gotten from Uniprot. Posttranslational modifications were confirmed using ScanProsite and then the output of Netsurf 2.0 was linked with ScanProsite output. It was done because for PTM analysis the amino acid or motif of protein on modification must exposed to the surface and should not buried in the structure.

Figure: Exposed and buried residues of METTL5 protein predicted by NetSurf2.0. Exposed residues are shown in red color upward elevation, and downward elevation in blue colored showed that they are buried residues; the helix is represented by orange color., pink lines represent coil and purple arrows represent strands.

In this study, 61 variants in ScanProsite and it was showed that 22 variants laid in the PTM sites. The NetSurf2.0 shows that 5 out of 22 variants were exposed to the surface. The exposed variants were further observed and visualized in the protein structure using the UCSF chimera.

PS00006 CK2_PHOSPHO_SITE Casein kinase II phosphorylation site :		
46 - 49:	TydD	
Predicted feature:		
MOD_RES	46	Phosphothreonine

In this motif, mutation at D49Y is disturbing the phosphorylation of the of the motif at Casein kinase II phosphorylation. Due to this variation, aspartate is replaced with tyrosine

residue that badly affects the motif and also affects the Casein kinase II phosphorylation site by preventing the phosphorylation of the motif.

Figure: Visual Representation of Casein kinase C phosphorylation site that taken from UCSF Chimera. The mutation p.D49Y represented in red color.

100 - 103:	TniD	
Predicted feature:		
MOD_RES	100	Phosphothreonine

In this motif, mutation at D103G is disturbing the phosphorylation of the motif at Casein kinase II phosphorylation. Due to this variation, aspartate is replaced with glycine residue that badly affects the motif and also affects the Casein kinase II phosphorylation site by preventing the phosphorylation of the motif.

Figure: Visual Representation of Casein kinase II phosphorylation site that taken from UCSF Chimera. The mutation p.D103G is represent in red color.

PS00008 MYRISTYL *N*-myristoylation site :

73 - 78: GAg1CV .

In the motif, ranging from 73-78, a missense mutation at L76W was disturbing the PTM mechanism of METTL5 gene. In this mutation lysine is replaced by tryptophan residue that badly affects myristoylation site of the motif.

Figure: Visual Representation of N-Myristoylation site taken from UCSF Chimera. The mutation p.L76W represented in green colour.

130 - 135: GTknNK .

In the motif, ranging from 130-135, a missense mutation at G130E was disturbing the PTM mechanism of METTL5 gene. In this mutation glycine is replaced by glutamate residue that badly affects myristoylation site of the motif.

Figure: Visual Representation of N-Myristoylation site taken from UCSF Chimera. The mutation p.G130E represented in red color.

Mutagenesis of METTL5 Gene by Using UCSF Chimera

UCSF chimera was used to analyze the effect and interaction of mutated residue with surrounding residues. It also done a comparison with wild-type residue. The final deleterious variants from missense analysis further checked for mutagenesis in UCSF chimera. It was done by mutating each residue one by one with its wild type and their

interaction checked. After analysis, most of the variants showed pseudo bonds/ clashes with surrounding residues. To remove those clashes, protein structure was minimized up to 15 minimization steps and 0 conjugate gradient steps. There were no contacts/ clashes found of wild type residue and mutated residue with there surrounding residue. The mutation in METTL5 gene has no effect on protein stability and structure

Figure: Mutagenesis analysis of METTL5 protein showed wild F207S doesn't clash with its surrounding residues

Splice Site Analysis of METTL5 gene

The splicing of mRNA can be affected by the mutation in splice site, which leads to loss of function of protein. In this study, I retrieved 283 variants from GnomAD and then I apply filters on two columns including "genome column" and "VEP annotation". After applying filters, 15/283 variants remained. To check the spliceogenicity of these variants, they

were further analyzed by CADD. After CADD analysis, variants with score greater than 10 were chosen and only 9/15 variants remained. These variants were further analyzed on SPiCE, SpliceAI and Mutation Taster.

SPiCE v2.1

SPiCE v2.1 is the computational tool used to analyze the pathogenic variants lying in splice

site region. The results were obtained in form of data and graphical representation. The threshold value is fixed, Pathogenic variants are present below the threshold value and neutral

variants are present above the threshold value. In this study, 9 variants from CADD annotation file were analyzed, only 4/9 were showing significant on splicing.

Figure: Graphical representation of output of SPiCE showing 4/9 variants as pathogenic. Variants lying under the blue line are non-pathogenic and variants lying above the blue line are pathogenic.

varID	SSF_annot_wt	SSF_annot_mut	SPICEprobability	SPICEinter_thrDia	CS
NM_014168g.170668375G>A	matrix AG	matrix AG	0.20772	high	1
NM_014168g.170672041G>A	matrix AG	matrix AG	0.984	high	2
NM_014168g.170672042A>G	matrix AG	matrix AG	0.00455	low	3
NM_014168g.170676087T>C	matrix GT	matrix GT	0.92730	high	4
NM_014168g.170677709A>T	matrix AG	matrix AG	0.02686	low	5
NM_014168g.170678448C>T	matrix GT	matrix GT	0.994	high	6
NM_014168g.170678572A>T	matrix AG	matrix AG	0.02686	low	7
NM_014168g.170680991C>G	matrix GT	matrix GT	0.02686	Outside SPICE interpretation	8
NM_014168g.170680992G>C	matrix GT	matrix GT	0.02686	Outside SPICE interpretation	9

Figure: SPiCE results in tabular form

Splice AI

Splice AI is an online tool. The results for each variant provided as Acceptor Loss, donor loss, acceptor gain, and donor gain. In my study, 9 variants were analyzed and they were predicted as nonpathogenic.

Table: Splice site variants analysis by using Splice AI

#Chrom:PosRef>Alt	Δ type	Δ score	pre-mRNA position
2:170668375G>A	Acceptor loss	0	
	Donor loss	0	
	Acceptor gain	0	-7
	Donor gain	0.04	360

2:170672041G>A	Acceptor loss	0	
	Donor loss	0	
	Acceptor gain	0	-3
	Donor gain	0.1	-54
2:170672042A>G	Acceptor loss	0.04	-4
	Donor loss	0	-55
	Acceptor gain	0	
	Donor gain	0	
2:170676067T>C	Acceptor loss	0	86
	Donor loss	0.12	4
	Acceptor gain	0	
	Donor gain	0.01	
2:170677789A>T	Acceptor loss	0.08	-6
	Donor loss	0	-187
	Acceptor gain	0.21	-126
	Donor gain	0	
2:170678448C>T	Acceptor loss	0	119
	Donor loss	0.58	5
	Acceptor gain	0.01	473
	Donor gain	0.01	17
2:170678572A>T	Acceptor loss	0.08	-5
	Donor loss	0	-119
	Acceptor gain	0.01	-56
	Donor gain	0.06	195
2:170680991C>G	Acceptor loss	0	159
	Donor loss	0	387
	Acceptor gain	0	
	Donor gain	0	8
2:170680992G>C	Acceptor loss	0	170
	Donor loss	0	7
	Acceptor gain	0.01	158
	Donor gain	0.03	33

Splice Ai: variants score >0.2 are pathogenic but they are all nonpathogenic because the score is less than 0.2.

Mutation Taster

It is an online tool to evaluate the disease-causing potential of sequence alterations. The variants obtained after CADD annotation was

analysed one by one and results were provided in form of probability of disease-causing potential of each variant. In this study, 2/9 variants show probability score of 1. 1/2

variant with splice site changes as mutation type. It was predicted that 2/9 variants were

significantly affecting the splice site of METTL5.

Table: Splice site variants analysis by Mutation Taster

#Chrom:PosRef>Alt	prediction	Phylop	Phastcon	splice site
2:170668375G>A	Benign	1.14	0.984	No change in splice sites
2:170672041G>A	Benign	4.70	1	No change in splice site
2:170672042A>G	Benign	0.22	0.996	No change in splice site
2:170676067T>C	Deleterious	3.905	1	Effect and Donor weakened
2:170677789A>T	Benign	1.704	0.004	No change in splice site
2:170678448C>T	Deleterious	1.648	0.978	No change in splice site
2:170678572A>T	Benign	0.172	0.151	No change in splice site
2:170680991C>G	Benign	-0.054	0.001	No change in splice site
2:170680992G>C	Benign	-0.017	0.001	No change in splice site

Table: Splice site variants analysis using CADD, Splice v2.1, splice Ai and Mutation Taster.

Nucleotide position	CA DD	SPICE v2.1	SPICE AI	Mutation Taster				
	Phred Score	Splice probability	SPICEinte_r_thr	Δ type	Δ score	pre-mRNA position	Mutation type	Probability
2:170668375 G>A	14.19	0.02772	High	Donor gain	0.04	360	Splice site	Benign
2:170672041 G>A	10.12	0.984	High	Donor gain	0.1	-54	Splice site	Benign
2:170672042 A>G	14.67	0.00455	Low	Acceptor loss	0.04	-4	Splice site	Benign
2:170676067 T>C	22.1	0.92738	High	Donor loss	0.12	4	Splice site	Deleterious
2:170677789 A>T	16.01	0.02686	Low	Acceptor gain	0.12	-126	Splice site	Benign

2:170678448 C>T	23.3	0.994	High	Acceptor gain	0.01	473	Splice site	Deleterious
2:170678572 A>T	14.64	0.02686	Low	Acceptor gain	0.1	-56	Splice site	Benign
2:170680991 C>G	12.73	0.02686	Outside Splice Interpretation	Acceptor loss	0	159	Splice site	Benign
2:170680992 G>C	12.76	0.02686	Outside Splice Interpretation	Acceptor gain	0.01	158	Splice site	Benign

Regulome DB 2.0

It is online database that evaluate the non-coding variants according to ranking. I retrieved the non-coding variants from GnomAD database. The input is RS ID no for this tool. The RS ID no of variants present in 3 prime UTRs region is used as input. Total 68 variants RS ID no upload on the database. 57 variants showed successfully by the database. 9 out of 57 show 2a ranking, 15 variants show 4 ranking, 25 variants show 5 ranking and 8 variants show 7 ranking.

Total 15 variants RS ID no of 5 prime UTRs region upload in the database. 2/15 variants show 2b ranking and remaining 13 variants show the 4 ranking. With the increasing ranks, the likelihood of the SNPs affecting the TF binding lessens. The rank 2a, 2b, 3a, 4 and 5 are support by TF binding + matched TF motif + matched DNase Footprint + DNase peak, TF binding + any motif + DNase Footprint + DNase peak, TF binding + any motif + DNase peak, TF binding + DNase peak, and TF binding or DNase peak data respectively by Regulome server.

Figure: Graphical representation of non-coding variants in 3 prime UTRs region of METTL5 gene.

- 2a ranking (TF binding + matched TF motif + matched DNase Footprint + DNase peak)
- 4 ranking (TF binding + DNase peak)
- 5 ranking (TF binding or DNase peak)
- 7 ranking (No effect on TF binding or DNase peak)

Figure: Graphical representation of Non-coding variants in 5 prime UTRs region by METTL5 gene.

- 2b ranking (TF binding + any motif + DNase Footprint + DNase peak)
- 4 ranking (TF binding + DNase peak)

Discussion

The intellectual developmental disorder is an autosomal recessive disorder related to severely below-average overall intellectual functioning together with abnormalities in adaptive behaviour. It is also associated with dysmorphic traits such as a coarse face, a wide nasal bridge, fleshy nares, and protruding lips. The prevalence of ID is more common in low-income countries. Approximately 1 to 3 percent of the global population has an intellectual disability. Studies revealed that mutation in METTL5 causes the intellectual developmental disorder. METTL5 gene is located on chromosome 2. Mutations in the METTL5 gene lead to the deregulation of this complex and its subunits resulting in pathogenic disorders. It can also affect the splicing and translation process for the enzyme leading to poor neurological and physical development. In this study, different computational approaches have been used to predict the most pathogenic variants of METTL5 gene and their effect on splicing, PTM site, stability and functionality has also

been studied. The bioinformatic approaches are getting more attention because they are time-saving and more productive as well. All available tools and software are based on specific algorithms. The algorithms of the computational tools are designed by computer scientists. The algorithms are input methods designed to create a database or tool. Every database has its own algorithm based on the output a scientist needs. The computational tools play a significant role to overcome all the challenges associated with a variety of diseases. In this study, I have used a variety of databases based on different algorithms to find highly deleterious variants of METTL5. I have done multiple analyses for the screening of pathogenic variants. This analysis includes missense analysis, splice site analysis, stability analysis, PTM analysis, and mutagenesis of the METTL5 gene.

For missense analysis, I retrieved pathogenic variants from GnomAD, variation viewer and dbSNP. After applying the filters on data of all these tools variants remained and these 296 variants were used as an input of CADD. These

296 variants ran on CADD and 196 variants remained in CADD output after applying filters. These 196 variants were further used for missense analysis by using MetaSNP tool. The combined file of all these missense tools showed 66 highly pathogenic variants of METTL5. In stability analysis, 66 highly pathogenic variants were analysed on Cupsat DynaMut and Duet for the prediction of destabilizing variants. Cupsat predicted that 44/61 destabilizing variants, DynaMut predicted that 28/61 destabilizing variants and Duet predicted 55/61 destabilizing variants and combine results showed.

In functional analysis, Mutpred tool was used to check the disturbance in the function of the protein and it predicted 60/61 as pathogenic. Most of the functional disturbances in pathogenic variants were Altered Metal-binding, Altered Transmembrane protein, and Altered Ordered interface. These changes can affect the molecular mechanism of METTL5. In PTM site analysis, ScanProsite is used to analyze highly pathogenic missense variants to check whether they are disturbing the Post translation modification sites. I ran these variants on ScanProsite and analyzed that 22/61 lay in the PTM site and then these 22 variants were further checked on NetSurf2.0 to check whether they are exposed or buried and showed that 5/22 were exposed to the surface METTL5 protein and remains were buried. In the N-Myristoylation site, two variants L76W and G130E were disturbing the PTM mechanism of the METTL5 gene. In the Casein kinaseII phosphorylation site, two variant D49Y and D103G lie which disturbs the motif. I have also observed and visualized these pathogenic variants in the protein structure using the UCSF chimera. I have also used UCSF chimera to check whether pathogenic variants produce clashes in protein structure and pathogenic variants were showed no clashes with the neighboring residues of METTL5 protein. After the missense analysis, I have also done the splice site analysis to check the variation at the splice region of the protein. For splice site analysis, I again retrieved 288 variants from GnomAd and after applying filters 15/288 remained and after running

those 15 variants on CADD only 9/15 remained.

These variants were further analysed on SPiCE, SpliceAI and Mutation Taster. SPiCE v2.1 showed that 4/13 were having significant on splicing. Based on score Variant NM_014168:g.170668375:G>A, NM_014168:g.170672041:G>A

NM_014168:g.170676067:T>C and NM_014168:g.170678448:C>T have high effect on the splicing of mRNA of METTL5 gene while remaining have low affect. Moreover, SpliceAI predicted all variants as nonpathogenic and Mutation Taster showed 1/9 variants were significantly affecting the splice site of METTL5 protein. It can predict that SNPs scoring 2 and 3 in Regulome ranking are affecting TF binding and are less likely to affect TF binding respectively, whereas SNPs have minimum binding evidence that scoring 4 and 5 in Regulome ranking. 9 out of 57 variants present in 3 prime UTRs region show 2a ranking, 15 variants show 4 ranking, 25 variants show 5 ranking and 8 variants show 7 ranking.

2/15 variants present in 5 prime UTRs region show 2b ranking and remaining 13 variants show the 4 ranking. All of these mutations have been considered as deleterious by using in silico tools and in the future scientists can directly use these mutations for the development of therapeutics against the disease-related METTL5 gene such as Autosomal Recessive Intellectual Developmental Disorder. Highly pathogenic variants predicted in this study can also be further checked or confirmed through wet lab analysis in animal models.

Conclusion

By using in silico approach for coding and noncoding variants analysis of METTL5 showed that protein function and stability affected by deleterious variants. In missense analysis, 196/884 variants predicted as pathogenic. In stability analysis, Cupsat tool predicted that 17 were stabilizing, 1 was no change and 43 were destabilizing. DynaMut tool predicted that 28 were destabilizing and 33 were stabilizing. Duet analysis predicted that 55 were destabilizing and 6 were stabilizing. In

UCSF CHIMERA 66 variants showed no clashes with neighbouring residues, 22/66 lied on the PTM site, 5/22 predicted to be exposed to the surface of METTL5 protein. In splice site analysis 4/9 variants were predicted to be disturbing the splice site of METTL5 gene, SpliceAI predicted all variants as nonpathogenic and Mutation Taster showed 1/9 variants were significantly affecting the splice site of METTL5 protein. The regulome DB analysis predicted that variants have low effect on the transcription site of the gene. This data can be helpful in the early detection of ID. This data can also be used in the development of novel treatments and therapeutics.

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